

“SYSTEMATIC PREVENTION OF CARDIOVASCULAR DISEASES”

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By focusing on early detection and risk assessment, healthcare providers can identify individuals at high risk for cardiovascular disease and intervene with targeted interventions to prevent disease progression. Lifestyle modifications, including healthy diet, regular exercise, smoking cessation, and stress management, can significantly reduce the risk of developing cardiovascular disease and improve overall cardiovascular health.

Furthermore, population-wide screenings and education campaigns can raise awareness about the importance of cardiovascular health and empower individuals to take control of their own health. Policy interventions, such as legislation to promote healthy environments and support for preventive healthcare services, can create a supportive infrastructure for systematic prevention efforts.

Data analyses revealed that the age group in question still includes a great number of people who are unaware of the relationship between nutrition and development (31.8%) or progression (18.0%) of heart diseases. Rejection of the relationship was most frequently expressed by those 40-49 years of age and those that were employed. The study also found that the role of nutrition modification was more frequently discussed between patients and physicians (54.7%) than patients and nurses (38.0%). An overwhelming majority of respondents considered information related to nutrition modification useful (93.0%).

Despite strong scientific evidence supporting the benefits of regular exercise for the prevention and management of cardiovascular disease (CVD), physical inactivity is highly prevalent worldwide. In addition to merely changing well-known risk factors for systemic CVD, regular exercise can also improve cardiovascular health through non-traditional mechanisms. Understanding the pathways through which exercise influences different physiological systems is important and might yield new therapeutic strategies to target pathophysiological mechanisms in CVD. This Review includes a critical discussion of how regular exercise can have antiatherogenic effects in the vasculature, improve autonomic balance (thereby reducing the risk of malignant arrhythmias), and induce cardioprotection against ischaemia-reperfusion injury,

independent of effects on traditional CVD risk factors. This Review also describes how exercise promotes a healthy anti-inflammatory milieu (largely through the release of muscle-derived myokines), stimulates myocardial regeneration, and ameliorates age-related loss of muscle mass and strength, a frequently overlooked non-traditional CVD risk factor. Finally, we discuss how the benefits of exercise might also occur via promotion of a healthy gut microbiota. We argue, therefore, that a holistic view of all body systems is necessary and useful when analysing the role of exercise in cardiovascular health.

In conclusion, systematic prevention plays a crucial role in the management of cardiovascular disease by addressing risk factors, promoting healthy behaviors, and empowering individuals to take control of their own health. By prioritizing and implementing systematic prevention measures, we can reduce the incidence and severity of cardiovascular disease and improve overall health and well-being for individuals and populations at risk.

Использованная литература:

1. Vera Olisarova 1, Valerie Tothova 2, Lenka Sedova 2, Sylva Bartlova 2, Ivana Chloubova 2, Helena Michalkova 2, Radka Prokesova 3, Marie Treslova 2 Assessment of the Perceived Relationship Between Healthy Nutrition and Cardiovascular Diseases by the Adult Czech Population High Blood Press Cardiovasc Prev. 2019 Feb;26(1):55-60. doi: 10.1007/s40292-019-00299-4. Epub 2019 Jan 18.
2. WHO A healthy diet is essential for good health and nutrition.
3. DiNicolantonio JJ, O'Keefe JH. Preventing Cardiovascular Disease. Prog Cardiovasc Dis. 2016 Mar-Apr;58(5):463. doi: 10.1016/j.pcad.2016.02.002. Epub 2016 Feb 11.PMID: 26875628 No abstract available.